

Research

Unraveling Commodity Price Forecasting: Insights from Chinese Stock Market Movements and Exchange Rate Fluctuations

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Abstract

The research focuses on the spillover effects of the Chinese stock market (CSM), foreign exchange (FEX) and commodities (Gold, Natural Gas, Oil). With the cross-quantilogram (CQ) method, daily returns are analyzed with a focus on market spillovers within varying conditions. It is established that spillover effects are specific to certain quantiles. In the case of strong market returns, Gold is quite positively affected by the CSM and mostly during most tumultuous periods, while negative spillovers on Gold were caused by a stronger dollar making the metal relatively expensive for foreign buyers. High quantiles of net returns on natural gas, where positive spillovers from CSM are also present. Additionally, a favorable USDCNY exchange rate increases local energy consumption. China is one of the most significant oil consumers and therefore oil displays high positive correlation to the CSM. The study cautions on both market diversification and currency movements to avoid the risks. Emphasize FEX stability and the correlation between stock and commodity prices to strengthen economies. The research assesses that further work is necessary on spillovers and on shock transmission in the context of deepening integration of emerging markets focusing on the still little examined futures and spot markets.

Keywords: Chinese Stock Market, Exchange rate, Commodity prices, Cross-quantilogram.

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1 Introduction

Current global economic volatility necessitates a consideration of the intricate relationships relationship between commodity prices (CMP), stock market performance (SMP), foreign exchange rates (FEX) has drawn the interest of a good number of economists and investors. Given the high degree of uncertainty embedded in CMP, it is critical to understand its fluctuations and the between investors' expectations and risk management (Cao and Ling 2022). Of utmost importance is the study of the connection between commodity prices and the China Securities Market (CSM) and the exchange rate (Jiang et al. 2016). This dynamic is most clearly observed in China, a significant force in both commodity consumption and financial markets. This is because China's position in commodity markets and economic power becomes instrumental in such analysis (Wang et al. 2021).

This is because China's position in commodity markets and economic power becomes instrumental in such analysis (Long et al. 2021). Commodities are scarce resources that have a great impact on industries but also on economies of nations and could have great broader impacts to the global economy (Salisu et al. 2019a). Apart from trading instruments or security, commodities are asset classes feeding international trading systems running the global economy.

The CSM, being one of the largest in the world (Wang et al. 2021), has shown impressive performance with its position in global financial markets strengthening over the years (Heep 2014). This performance of the CSM is, however, subject to a number of variables pegged on the economy such as domestic level, the government policies enacted, and trends observable in the international scene. But the linkage between CMP and CSM has been widely researched in these studies (Johnson and Soenen 2009; Nair et al. 2015; Jiang et al. 2016; Salisu et al. 2019a; Ayres et al. 2020), and quite a considerable amount of knowledge on this cause-effect relationship can be beneficial. Such insights are important for us to understand the possible impacts of these changes in the CMP structure on the share market situation and vice versa, and to explain the impact of the share market oscillations on the commodity prices. Goldstein (2004), for instance, draws attention to the relevance of foreign exchange rates effects when looking at the trade imbalances of China, focusing also on the setting of the Chinese currency, the Renminbi or Yuan. Companies that participate in international trade and are engaged in commodity production, export and import, in particular, should not ignore the impact of exchange rate movements, as they can be substantial (Offiong et al. 2016). Hence, the prices of commodities may be affected as a result of changes in foreign exchange.

As a result, the research in this paper is important because it adds to the existing literature by attempting to forecast CMP, and analyzing the determinants CSM and FEX of the forecast. The introduction of Cross-Quantilogram (CQ) techniques by Han et al. (2016) has transformed the econometrician's world, giving them new and useful perspectives. Such methods will be employed in this research with the aim of establishing the direction of the impact of changes in CSM and FEX on the changes in CMP. The study will seek not only to establish the direction of the relationship of CMP to CSM and FEX but also seek to establish the cause-and-effect relationships and factors that explain this relationship.

The interplay between this research topic and the economy's macro aspects provides significant motivation and relevance for the narrow examination of the research area. CMP engender profound impact on various spheres of the global economy; hence it is important to ascertain the predictability of these metrics for effective decision making (Salisu et al. 2019a). Additionally, Wang et al. (2021) further emphasize the need to explore the linkages between these measures due to the nature of integration of the global commodity markets and the important position that China takes in the market. These interactions are not only important for understanding the degree of CMP predictability, but they also provide important explanations of how the Chinese economy and its financial markets function. Understanding these dynamics not only deepens knowledge of CMP predictability but also offers key insights into the broader workings of the Chinese economy and financial markets (Jiang et al. 2016).

This research investigates the correlations between the CSM and the USDCNY exchange rate to provide predictive analytics beneficial to investors and policymakers. Substantial research has investigated the predictability of CMP and its relationships with SMP and FEX. Bernard et al. (2008) and Wang et al. (2013) conducted studies employing mean-

reverting models for commodity trend forecasting and identifying correlations between commodity and stock markets, respectively, with a focus on energy prices in the latter. Cashin et al. (2004) similarly demonstrated the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on commodity prices via trade mechanisms. Yet, these studies often overlook non-linear dynamics and the unique role of China's markets, leaving gaps in understanding how these factors interact under diverse conditions.

For investors, traders, and policymakers, research of this type has essential practical consequences, improving their understanding and facilitating better decision making and risk control, as well as the formulation of robust policies (Ayres et al. 2020). The research seeks to explain the complex and dynamic relationships that exist between CMP, CSM and FEX so that global trends in the economy are well comprehended enabling decision makers to appreciate the intricacies of commodity markets (Offiong et al. 2016).

The results of this research do indeed stand to enhance the debate with regards to the CMP predictability literature. Additionally, they could also shed light in the activities of the Chinese economy as well as the international capital markets (Wang et al. 2021). Participants of the commodity markets such as investors, traders and even the policy makers would find the derived conclusions of the research to be meaningful as it could help them appreciate the intricate connections between these indicators (Salisu et al. 2019a). As a result, however, persons charged with the responsibility of making decisions and managing risks through commodity trade and investment in international markets will be in a position to enhance their choices as well as strategize better.

2 Literature review

A substantial number of studies have been undertaken regarding this relationship and its features. In this respect, we have made comprehensive studies on various aspects of this relationship, for instance, focusing on the ability to forecast commodity prices, and exploring effects of stock markets and foreign currency exchange rates on the level of commodity prices. Many researchers took two or more steps in the framework of this site, and as a result earned a valuable new understanding of what is perhaps a complex interaction between stock markets and exchange rates.

2.1 Commodity Predictability

Different approaches and methods have been used in numerous studies to investigate the predictability of CMP (Calude et al. 2005; Bernard et al. 2008; Ding and Zhang 2020; Zhang et al. 2020; Antwi et al. 2022; Baser et al. 2023). This is illustrated through the work of An et al. (2023), Assessing the impact of including both dynamic topic sentiment features and time series modal features constructed from the data as well as structural breaks into prediction models remains a key area of focus. The findings made here imply that there is a potential benefit in the integration of text mining methods along with the comprehensive feature sets in improving the precision of forecasting prices of commodities especially in agriculture. Following the work of Shahwan & Lemke (2005), the specific objectives are the use of the self-organizing data mining tools and Elman neural network for prediction of commodity prices and assessment of their performance relative to the benchmark ARIMA model. One of the study conclusions is the ability of neural network methods such as Elman in predicting CMP. At the same time, it is confirmed that other deep learning algorithms may also be useful for that purpose. Moreover, Ben Ameer et al. (2023) conducted an investigation into the potential of different deep learning algorithms for predicting CMP. methods are also proposed to be useful, and the authors argue for advantages of the method as a forecasting tool. To the authors and investors including policymakers, these results have practical implications for making revisions of public policy in response to shocks like the Russian Ukrainian war. Also, Ding & Zhang (2020) note liquidity in the context that information might not be obvious in the price processes of less liquid markets. Therefore, while predicting prices in underdeveloped commodity markets, it becomes crucial to examine both the price and liquidity of other markets. On the other hand, the prices of oil and other liquid commodities can be correctly predicted only by cross-market prices without the inclusion of any specific variables.

2.2 Commodity Prices and Stock Market

A thorough analysis has been done in regards to the relationship between the two indicators. Bernard et al. (2008) point out that the mean reverting model with a stochastic yield model framework does yield better results and gives the expected risk a meaning with respect to pricing behavior. Similarly, Aumeboonsuke (2021) explain the variances of the CMP in respect to energy resources and precious metals, in turn, affect the performance of the stock market in Thailand.

Furthermore, Wang et al. (2013) also recognizes the persistent relations between different commodity and stock markets, with the commodity indices being prominent in the determination of stock market indices. However, they acknowledge the great influence that the US stock market has on the commodity indices. The study done by Ding and Zhang (2020) found out that there is a long-run price equilibrium in the oil and industrial metal markets. In opposition, a stability condition is not realized in the agricultural and gold markets owing to interferences from liquidity in the cross-markets. Furthermore, Kang et al. (2020) provide the visualization on the reciprocal relationship in terms of the impact caused by shocks of the commodity market and the volatility of the stock exchange, laying stress on the global financial crises. Furthermore, Iscan (2015) broadens the Parsian argument and focus's on the effect of such CMP in relation to the performance of the stock market thus offering important guidance to investors and policy makers. In the work conducted by Mongale and Hinaunye Eita (2014) the authors suggested that SMP in South Africa is influenced by CMP and a macroeconomic variable with respect to a positive correlation. More evidence was provided by Salisu, Isah, et al. (2019) concerning the idea that stock returns could be better predicted with the use of CMP rather than with other models. Enilov et al. (2023), took this a step further by explaining the relationship between global shocks of CMP and the national financial markets, accounting for country and the global commodity super-cycles. Ntantamis and Zhou, (2015) outline that only a moderate amount of evidence concerning the relationship of the cycles of commodity prices and the prices of the stocks of related companies was found. CSM's influence has been presented to be less powerful than previously thought in the international commodity market by Wen et al. (2019). Even with the CSM, their research indicates that there are still benefits to diversification in constructing portfolios.

2.3 Commodity Prices and Exchange Rate

The relationships between CMP and FEX have been deeply explored in the literature due to the great volume of works on this theme. Many scholars have shown the correlation, the market cash positions being the most volatile proxies of future exchange rate changes. (Buah and Sika 2017; Salisu et al. 2019a) extend the understanding of the role of persistence, endogeneity, conditional heteroscedasticity, asymmetries, or structural breaks in their forecasts and make better predictions. Furthermore, John et al. (2012) presents an empirical model where he finds that a factor-based model outperforms the random walk model. In this model, the US nominal exchange rate is credited as the initial common component. Besides, the heat of commodity prices in export driven economies has been supported by global power studies by (Zou et al. 2017; Haider et al. 2023). Moreover, according to Bashar and Kabir (2013) commodity prices, interest rates, and the Global Financial Crisis were determined to be comprehensively significant determinants of exchange rates. What is more, the relationship is described as dynamic in the literature and it can be noticed that strength and direction of the relationship does change over time as shown by (Cashin et al. 2004; Harri et al. 2009). In conclusion, these conclusions show a direct impact between the variables, emphasizing the importance of integrating commodity market influence into both the examination and forecasting of the movements of the exchange rates.

The scrutiny of literature quite considerably elucidates the existence of a knowledge lacuna in terms of application of econometric model as developed by Han et al. (2016) We employ the CQ approach using CSM and FEX to predict the CMP's dynamics. Though there are studies regarding the relationship between the variables CMP, SMP and FEX, the application of CQ methodology in this role however is inadequately covered in literature. The CQ approach is a quite novel econometric method that has only recently been used to determine the predictive strength of one variable over another across the entire distribution of the other variable. By employing this methodology, CMP in relation to CSM and exchange rates can be illustrated regarding the strengths most likely to be associated with their predictability. For example, it can be used to examine whether certain variables anticipate each other across different quantiles or not. The relevance of this constellation of research problems is especially high for investors, policymakers and other market participants in China, which is also the country of this study, where commodity markets are quite important. In studying the Chinese Stock Market and the exchange rates, this means researchers have the opportunity to shed light on the causality and predictability of these relationships. The research conducted in the area of predicting asset price movements in the CSM and FEX using CQ methodology would be significant in contributing to the literature as well as for practice in commodity markets.

3 Methodology

This study period starts from September 17, 2014, and ends on June 08, 2023, with daily observations and extends to the study of CSM members including the Shanghai Stock Exchange, the Hang Seng Index, the CSI 300, and the Shenzhen Stock Exchange, as well as the USDRMB exchange rate in terms of its contributions to CMP.

Linton and Whang (2007) developed the Quantilogram to measure the extent and characteristics of directional motion in time series for any variety of quantiles. After this, Han et al. (2016) advanced the univariate Quantilogram and more recently presented the bivariate CQ. The CQ technique is adopted here in order to investigate the relationships among the quantiles of a number of variables. The CQ methodology measures correlation in a non-parametric way and is considered both precise and valid in assessing the interrelation of variables. The cross-quantile Cq approach a.k.a Thickness Measures of the relative attitude of X to Y is quite distinct from the classical correlation, as its focus is the examination of the patterns among variables over a number of discrete distributions. This methodology is dedicated to detect the asymmetries in the dependence structure between random variables spread over different quantiles. Through these CQ approaches, one is able to understand that relation, not in a one-dimensional sense, but rather understand how the relation behaves at many points along the distribution of the variables. A key condition for the application of the CQ method is that the variables have a theoretical process that is stationary. This condition is essential for the reliability of correlation estimates derived from the CQ approach. In this presentation, we provide examples of heatmaps and show how they are used to analyze cross-quantile correlation estimates. The correlation analysis with distinct lags is depicted through the heatmap analysis of the variables. In relation to these fluctuation theories, the heatmap helps in the comprehension of the variation in the dependence structure of the constituents with regard to the various quantile and order lags.

Heat maps assist in understanding the CQ concept that describes the relationship between any two distributions of quantiles without conforming to any of their specific conditions. This makes it easy for Queteletian measures of concentration to capture the entirety of the dependence structure encoded in CQ estimations. Heatmaps are an effective tool for depicting the interaction among variables that involve the quantile distribution. CQ between time series is important in assessing the predictability of the time series variables. Based on the heatmap, we can demonstrate how the relationship between the different variables changes across various quantiles. Each heatmap cell depicts the volume of the CQ relation with one variable at mix quantiles against a specific quantile of the other variable. The color scale in the subordinate heatmap has an important role in deciding how intensely two variables are related. This method allows us to accurately measure the intensity of the correlation because the differences in shades of the scale represent this, the darker shades the stronger the correlation, the lighter shades the weaker the correlation.

Within the CQ framework, y_t and x_t can be both treated as theoretical processes that do not exhibit any change over time. Taking into account the theory of $y_t = (y_{1,t}, y_{2,t})^T \in \mathbb{R}^{d_1} \times \mathbb{R}^{d_2}$, it is possible to describe the function and a conditional distribution function as $F_{y_i|x_i}(x_{it})$ and $q_{i,t}(\tau_i) = \inf\{\vartheta: F_{y_i|x_i}(\vartheta|x_{it}) \geq \tau_i\}$ for any $\tau_i \in (0,1)$. The fundamental step of the CQ approach lies in the first few moments of estimating the empirical process of the quantile-hit. As stated by this process there are two events which are $y_{it} \leq q_{1,t}(\tau_1)$ and $y_{2,t-g} \leq q_{2,t-g}(\tau_2)$ which have serial dependency. The cross-correlation between different quantile-hits can be established using the second function.

$$\rho_\tau(g) = \frac{E[\varphi_{\tau_1}(y_{1,t} - q_{1,t}(\tau_1))\varphi_{\tau_2}(y_{2,t-g} - q_{2,t-g}(\tau_2))]}{\sqrt{E[\varphi_{\tau_1}^2(y_{1,t} - q_{1,t}(\tau_1))]} \sqrt{E[\varphi_{\tau_2}^2(y_{2,t-g} - q_{2,t-g}(\tau_2))]}} \quad (1)$$

In the CQ approach, the quantile hit process is specified as $\varphi_y = 1[u < 0] - \gamma$, where u refers to the quantile hit indicator. This function shows whether an observed measure exceeds ($u \geq 0$) or fails to exceed ($u < 0$) is a parameter to modify the measure of association. When focusing on the quantile-hit process, time $t - g$ is relevant, where g is the number of periods before and after the chosen time. In this way we can measure the impact of the variables to the given time period while taking into consideration the relative positions of each variable as measured by the quantiles. The correlation of the quantile-hit process is described with $\rho_\tau(g)$. This measure of correlation evaluates the strength of the basic variable metric and enables the ability to analyze the interplay between separate quantiles of the investigated characteristics.

With the view to in creating the sample analogue of the CQ, Han et al. (2016) take up the linear quantile regression by Koenker and Bassett (1978) for the sake of simplicity. In order to find an empirical analogy to $\hat{\rho}_\tau(g)$, We undertake the relevant computations. The particular method which was adopted to obtain my first estimation of $q_i(\tau_i)$ was estimating quantile $\hat{q}_i(\tau_i)$ which was contained in the sample problem. For reasons of symmetry and continuity, we regard this as a minimization problem and seek an appropriate design for this purpose.

$$\hat{q}_i(\tau_i) = \arg \min_{\beta_i \in \mathbb{R}^{d_i}} \sum_{k=1}^p \delta_{\tau_i}(y_{it} - q_i) \quad (2)$$

Where $\delta_{\tau_i}(x) \equiv x(\tau - 1[x < 0])$. Then let:

$$\hat{\rho}_{\tau}(g) = \frac{\sum_{t=g+1}^T \varphi_{\tau_1}(y_{1,t} - \hat{q}_{1,t}(\tau_1))\varphi_{\tau_2}(y_{2,t-g} - \hat{q}_{2,t-g}(\tau_2))}{\sqrt{\sum_{t=g+1}^T \varphi_{\tau_1}^2(y_{1,t} - q_{1,t}(\tau_1))} \sqrt{\sum_{t=g+1}^T \varphi_{\tau_2}^2(y_{2,t-g} - q_{2,t-g}(\tau_2))}} \quad (3)$$

The CQ method is applied in the process of establishing and testing the existence of directional predictions of two time series. The Metric C serves as an index in terms of the existence of directional relationships. For example, the event $y_{1t} \leq q_{1,t}(\tau_1)$ and $y_{2,t-g} \leq q_{2,t-g}(\tau_2) = 0$ serves as a metric for cross-dependence or the notion of predicting directional dependence. Furthermore, $\rho_{\tau}(g) = 1$ indicates the presence of quantile or directional prediction. It has already been discussed above, it relates to the correlation between the conditional dependence structures and the value 0. The test null hypotheses for the correlation measures of interest are based on the assumption that they are significantly different from zero. The null hypothesis ($H_0: \rho_{\tau}(1) = \dots = \rho_{\tau}(p) = 0$) is devoid of any difference explanations from ingoing zero. On the other hand the alternative hypothesis ($H_1: \rho_{\tau}(g) \neq 0$ for some $g \in \{1 \dots \dots p\}$) posits that there are differences apart from zero significance value. In testing the null hypothesis, reference is made to the Box-Ljung test based on Han et al. (2016). This statistical procedure allows for the testing of the null hypothesis in question, therefore making it possible for drawing conclusions. So as to carry out this analysis, the Box-Ljung test adopts a certain specification.

$$\hat{Q}\tau(p) = T(T + 2) \sum_{g=1}^p \hat{\rho}^2(g) / T - g \quad (4)$$

In this case, a logarithmic form is used to express all the returns on a daily basis. The daily returns are calculated using:

$$r_t = \ln(CP_t - CP_{t-1} / CP_{t-1}) \quad (5)$$

Where r_t , denotes the return on day t, CP_t shows the closing price on day t and CP_{t-1} is the closing price of day t-1.

4 Result and discussion

The time-series used in this study have their corresponding description statistics presented in Table 1. reveal key insights into the behavior of these indicators over the studied period. The mean returns are generally low, with commodities like Gold showing slight positive trends, while Oil and HSI has a negative mean return, indicating a downward trajectory. Volatility, as measured by standard deviation, is highest for Oil (6.4006%), followed by Natural Gas (3.1683%), signifying substantial price fluctuations, while Gold exhibits the lowest volatility. Among stock indices, CHL has the highest volatility, and HSI the lowest, with the exchange rate (USDRMB) showing notable stability. Skewness reveals asymmetry in returns, with Oil showing extreme negative skewness (-36.6821), indicating a tendency for significant price drops, while Natural Gas and CHL exhibit positive skewness, suggesting more frequent upward movements. Kurtosis values are exceptionally high across most variables, particularly Oil (1689.8268), signaling frequent extreme price movements and non-normal distribution patterns. The Jarque-Bera test confirms non-normality for all variables, supported by the high skewness and kurtosis figures. According to Han et al. (2016), for the CQ method to be applicable, it is essential that the data series adhere to a stationary stochastics process. Therefore, in order to test the stationary property of our variable, we employ two widely-accepted stationary tests, specifically the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) and the Philip-Perron (PP) (Phillips and Perron, 1986) tests. Both the ADF and PP tests indicate that all variables are stationary at the 1% significance level, ensuring reliability for time series analysis. Overall, these results highlight the significant volatility, skewness, and non-normality in the data, which are crucial considerations for predictive models like the CQ method employed in this study.

Table 1 Description statistics

Variable	Mean (%)	Standard Deviation (%)	Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera	ADF	PP
CMP(GOLD)	0.0178	0.7790	0.0797	7.0925	367.86***	-40.665(0)***	-57.761(0)***
CMP(NAT)	0.0395	3.1683	0.9722	20.1666	443.32***	-42.366(0)***	-61.764(0)***

CMP(OIL)	-0.0890	6.4006	-36.6821	1689.8268	N/A	-41.546(0)***	-43.275(0)***
CSM(SSE)	0.0146	1.0998	-1.1716	11.8393	864.03***	-40.721(0)***	-56.312(0)***
CSM(HSI)	-0.0028	1.0854	0.1990	6.8509	373.24***	-41.414(0)***	-57.295(0)***
CSM(CHL)	0.0056	1.5219	1.0270	8.8435	726.36***	-39.735(0)***	-55.824(0)***
CSM(SZS)	0.0224	1.3467	-0.7126	13.1761	691.36***	-42.806(0)***	-56.624(0)***
FEX(CNY)	0.0050	0.2287	-0.1012	9.6049	443.32***	-41.344(0)***	-59.108(0)***

Note: *** denotes statistical significance at the 1% level.

The empirical results will be presented in two subsections for clearer organization. In the first subsection, the relationship between these indicators is explored in terms of cross-quantile dependence both the heatmap and daily return CQ. In the second subsection, we illustrate the CMP's connection with other assets, specifically CSM and FEX, by utilizing subsample estimations in the roiling CQ.

Fig. 1 represents heatmaps of the cross-quantilogram correlations, which provide a visual representation of the relationships between these indicators across different quantiles. Every cell in the grid of the heatmap corresponds to the correlation between the variables at the respective quantiles level. The legend on the left-hand part of the display explains the strength and direction of these relationships.

Fig. 1. analyzes the cross-quantilogram correlation, which shows how the Stock Market of China, exchange rate and commodities prices are related. The display also has a scale of colors on the left which focuses on the direction of the relationship.

red is the most preferable color as it indicates a strong positive correlation. These heatmaps make it possible to analyze the cross-quantile range correlations so that their different dependencies can be visually represented and analyzed even if only qualitatively. One example is how correlations at lower quantiles reflect the sensitivity of stock market indices to certain commodities during downturns while higher quantiles reflect the same relationship but during expansions or boom periods.

The heatmaps effectively depict the temporal relationships among such indicators and demonstrate how the movements of stock indices and currency rates affect the volatility of commodity price forecasting in the different regimes. This goes hand in hand with what has been done, for example by Wang et al. (2013) and Ding and Zhang (2020) who focus on the existence of long and short relationships among these indicators. Furthermore, the CQ methodology implemented here is of great importance for the empirical analysis since it enables revealing the non-constant and non-linear associations which are disregarded by the average correlation models (Han et al. 2016).

In particular, the use of CQ heatmaps enables us to explore these relationships thoroughly up to different lag lengths which further helps the analysis of predictability of commodity markets. When we observe or locate the presence of strong associations around certain quantile ranges, this quite positively helps us in conceptualizing the fact that how some particular segments of the market movements can influence other segments, especially in stressed or turbid economic situations (Bernard et al. 2008; An et al. 2023). The issues related to cross relationships in other types of market stress conditions in the heat maps suggest some implications for investors and policy makers, since the problems observed across various market conditions need to be addressed pragmatically.

The Gold analysis revealed strong daily returns in CSM and Gold in the 24, 25 and 26. Quantiles, which indicates a positive correlation. From these findings we can say that when stock market performance in China is high, gold returns will also tend to be high. This kind of positive correlation can be attributed to the fact that gold acts as a hedge against uncertainty in the world markets. In times of uncertainty – be it geopolitical or economic – investors may shift to Gold as a safe haven driving its demand, and returns higher (Bernard et al. 2008; Salisu et al. 2019a). This is in agreement with previous trends whereby gold prices increased concurrently with demand for stock markets during world financial turmoil since gold secures against chaos in the market. In as much as this is the case, the lower quantiles depicts opposite trends suggesting that gold returns are less affected by the downturns in CSM. This is in line with some literature stating that gold performs as a hedge during global turbulence and inflation times rather than routine market corrections periods (Gatfaoui 2016). For example, Gold's image as a "crisis commodity" has been said to be reinforced only under extreme circumstances in the markets or major shifts in the macroeconomic (Wang et al. 2021). On the contrary, it is unexpected that there is a negative correlation between the USDCNY exchange rate and gold returns in the higher quantiles. This means that if the dollar appreciates, the gold returns tend to decline as it becomes more expensive. This is something that ought to be taken into consideration during times when the dollar sees an extreme appreciation. Dollar's appreciation makes requires less number of dollars to purchase gold. It also means that gold appreciates in price which lowers demand and thus lowers return on the asset (Buah and Sika 2017). This relationship, on the other hand, is consistent with previous studies focusing some gold, which is purchased in dollars, has an inversely relationship with dollar value (Uddin et al. 2019). However, middle and lower quantiles more or less do not show any or very weak correlation which suggest that Gold is at the most times safe during destabilizing exchange rate periods.

The dependence structure between the CSM and Natural Gas returns are lots stronger at middle and higher quantiles. This substantiates the hypothesis that returns on Natural Gas would increase if the Chinese exchanged market performs satisfactorily as demand for energy resources increases owing to economical expansionism. Jiang et al. (2016). write that Natural Gas constitutes a large segment of China's industry especially in the making of electricity and heating which is directly in relation to the growth of industrial output and economic growth. Salisu et al. (2019b) observed a very strong correlation between global demand for Natural Gas supply in the Middle East and stock market growth, especially, when the sentiment of the market is high as demand for this fuel resource escalates. The same relationship which assists industries in increasing their output is responsible for raising energy prices as well – supply shortages resulting from increasing consumption always follow bolstering stock markets. Ntantamis and Zhou (2015) in this context establish, that other energy markets, including natural gas, are subject to the same logic because gas demand is inevitably rising in parallel with growth of the economy measured by stock returns. USDCNY evidence against a natural gas returns dependence structure follows a slightly different pattern but still magnitudes are the same, although for the middle quantiles, USDCNY proved more positive than natural gas returns. The implication of this finding is that natural gas returns are enhanced by a USDCNY exchange rate increment. This is somewhat bewildering, given that a stronger yuan should theoretically decrease China's cost of importing natural gas, which is sold in US dollars. But the positive relation

is more likely to other variables such as the speculative uvnwanina in energy market or the increase in demand of natural gas in China which may be more than the two imnas of the strong yuan on x gas imports cost (Bashar and Kabir 2013). Also, As China is increasing the share of natural gas in its energy mix, especially when it tries to cut back on coal consumption and convert to cleaner energy sources, natural gas prices may go up even if the exchange rate rate moves in the right direction (Heep 2014).

The Oil analysis also indicates the existence of very strong movement correlations with the daily returns CSM daily returns especially in the higher quantiles this means that as the CSM does well, Oil returns do also. China consumes oil the second most in the world, and performance of its stock exchange is sometimes indicative of general industrial activity, building and transportation activities all of which in effect increases the demand for oil (Nair et al. 2015). The positive relationship that exists between the CSM and Oil returns when China's stock returns are high indicates the strong expansion of China's economy and its influence on oil consumption in the world (Johnson and Soenen 2009). This is consistent with research which positions China amongst the rapidly rising economies having a huge dependence for a global energy provision and markets, especially oil, as industrialization and urban areas growth ratio picks (Wang et al. 2021). It is also very surprising that oil returns also have a non-linear relationship with the USDCNY, since they are positively correlated in the middle quantiles versus negatively correlated in the higher quantiles. Concerning this issue, it is likely that moderate appreciation of the yuan would support higher oil returns by reducing the cost of purchasing oil, which is valued in United States dollars (Wang et al. 2021). Further, however, at the higher quantiles, the relationship grows negative, which might be linked to speculative trading or global market corrections during periods of extreme level of exchange (Ding and Zhang 2020) or vice versa. One case, once USDCNY sudden reaches extreme levels, China might incur a low price in purchasing oil hence bring down oil returns. This non-linear aspect indicates that there is the possibility of some quasi-free market efficiencies in the oil market as most macroeconomic fundamentals prices like supply and demand, oil price, and inflation, are often in place but are still quite difficult to predict in those terms.

From this analysis, some interesting results are seen. One of the most interesting is the unexpected negative relationship between the USDCNY and Gold returns in the upper quantile ranges, where it is observed that gold returns decrease as the dollar appreciates against yuan. Such a view could be an indicator of a possible change in investor preferences towards different assets or commodities as the Chinese economy grows and investors look for higher returns (Buah and Sika 2017). On the other hand, Returns on Natural Gas investments display an unexpected positive correlation with the CNY Across quantiles which is quite the reverse as we would expect that the stronger the yuan, the lower the import volume. This indicates that it is increasing local demand or speculation that is pushing natural gas returns up notwithstanding the attractive exchange rate (Bashar and Kabir 2013). For Oil, the non-linear relationship with the CNY demonstrates positive correlations in the middle quantiles and negative in the higher quantiles, reflects the nature of the oil market as well as the sensitivity it has towards exchange and global economic variables (Ding and Zhang 2020). Last but not least, the positive correlation established between Oil returns and CSM in the higher quantiles reinforced the conclusions made above, focus on the health of China's economy as a major determinant for global oil consumption and its pricing in periods of economic health (Johnson and Soenen 2009).

Figure 2 presents compelling findings indicating a positive correlation between CSM and gold, with significant 1-day return spillovers observed across all three quantiles. These results align with the outcomes displayed in the left panel of Figure 1. However, it is important to highlight that the strength of the correlation diminishes notably after a 24-hour period. Regarding the spillover effect from FEX to gold, it is evident that daily returns exhibit negativity. This suggests that there is limited predictability in terms of directional relationships. Specifically, when CSM indicates a midpoint to top return in gold futures, FEX gold futures tend to demonstrate a bottom to midpoint to top return in the opposite direction on the same trading day. Analyzing the 24-hours quantile link of the return series reveals that the median quantile shows a slightly stronger correlation compared to the bottom and top quantiles. The statistical significance of the quantile correlation is supported by the test statistics obtained from the portmanteau test. It should be noted that the quantile correlation demonstrates significance and positivity exclusively for the 1-day period in gold. Across all three quantiles, the strength of the 1-day lead-lag correlation remains consistently prominent.

Likewise, the figure 3 depicts another important outcome: an observable and robust one day predictability from CSM to natural gas futures. This predictability seems to be true for more than half of the three quantiles examined. Also, for the examined quantiles, the data in the FEX show over one day FEX predicts negative f values for the natural gas futures market. The results exhibited in figure 4 also portray what appears to be an important predictive sense transfer effect from CSM to oil futures for daily returns, and this was observed in all three quantiles. On the other hand, FEX data confirm statistically substantial negative forecast lead from EFX to oil futures within one day lag across the three quantiles.

Fig. 2 Daily Return Spillovers from Chinese stock market and exchange rate to gold. The results are presented for three different quantiles: the low quantile ($\alpha = 0.1$) in the left panel, the median quantile ($\alpha = 0.5$) in the middle panel, and the high quantile ($\alpha = 0.9$) in the right panel. A lag of $\rho = 20$, corresponding to the average trading days per month, is considered.

Note: In the graph, the presence of red dashed lines indicates the 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals. These intervals are generated from 1,000 bootstrapped replicates and serve as a benchmark for the absence of directional predictability. If the observed spillovers fall within these confidence intervals, it suggests that there is no significant directional relationship present.

NATURAL GAS

Fig. 3 Daily Return Spillovers from Chinese stock market and exchange rate to natural gas. The results are presented for three different quantiles: the low quantile ($\alpha = 0.1$) in the left panel, the median quantile ($\alpha = 0.5$) in the middle panel, and the high quantile ($\alpha = 0.9$) in the right panel. A lag of $\rho = 20$, corresponding to the average trading days per month, is considered.

Note: In the graph, the presence of red dashed lines indicates the 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals. These intervals are generated from 1,000 bootstrapped replicates and serve as a benchmark for the absence of directional predictability. If the observed spillovers fall within these confidence intervals, it suggests that there is no significant directional relationship present.

In most cases, it seems that the daily return spillover is bi-directional, meaning there is an exchange of returns between two entities. Additionally, this spillover effect is characterized by a short-lived quantile correlation that is statistically significant, particularly for a 1-day time frame. The transmission of signals from the CSM and FEX to CMP is typically more robust, particularly when it comes to oil, gold, and natural gas. The correlation between the median quantiles shows a stronger relationship in certain cases, in contrast to the lower and upper quantiles.

OIL

Fig. 4 Daily Return Spillovers from Chinese stock market and exchange rate to oil. The results are presented for three different quantiles: the low quantile ($\alpha = 0.1$) in the left panel, the median quantile ($\alpha = 0.5$) in the middle panel, and the high quantile ($\alpha = 0.9$) in the right panel. A lag of $\rho = 20$, corresponding to the average trading days per month, is considered.

Note: In the graph, the presence of red dashed lines indicates the 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals. These intervals are generated from 1,000 bootstrapped replicates and serve as a benchmark for the absence of directional predictability. If the observed spillovers fall within these confidence intervals, it suggests that there is no significant directional relationship present.

Given the dynamic nature of the commodities futures markets during the period of September 17, 2014, to June 08, 2023, it is important to take into consideration the fluctuations and changes that occurred. Within this specific subsection, we have prepared a comprehensive rolling CQ analysis for three different commodities. One of the benefits of performing a rolling analysis is the ability to identify potential structural changes in the time series, especially in response to major market events. Additionally, this analysis provides a reliable method to verify the results obtained from the entire sample.

Fig. 5 Rolling Cross-Quantilogram daily return for gold. The graph specifically examines the effect from the Chinese Stock Market and Exchange Rate to Gold, with a focus on the 24-hours ahead rolling. The analysis is conducted at three quantiles: a bottom level ($\alpha=0.1$), a midpoint ($\alpha=0.5$) and a top ($\alpha=0.9$) from the left to right.

Figures 5 to 7 present the rolling CQ results for three commodities. Each figure consists of multiple panels arranged from top to bottom, representing the 24-hours-ahead spillover from various sources such as SSE, HSI, CHL, SZS, and CNY to three different quantiles. These figures provide comprehensive insights into the interconnections among these variables. To generate each data point in the figures, the rolling method described earlier is employed, where a rolling window is used to calculate the CQ. In the figures, the black dots represent the rolling CQ for 24-hours spillovers, reflecting the strength of the interconnections between the variables. Moreover, the hollow squares depicted in the graph play a significant role. We represent the 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals, which are derived from 1,000 bootstrapped replications. These intervals serve as benchmarks for assessing whether predictability is present or absent.

Fig. 6 Rolling Cross-Quantilogram Daily Return Spillovers for natural gas. The top panel of the graph specifically examines the spillover effect from the Chinese Stock Market and Exchange Rate to natural gas, with a focus on the 1-day ahead rolling spillover. The analysis is conducted at three quantiles: a low level ($\alpha=0.1$), a median ($\alpha=0.5$) and ($\alpha=0.9$) from the left to right.

comprehensive analysis of the entire sample, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the spillover effects among different markets. Firstly, the spillover effects from FEX to gold are generally more significant compared to those from CSM. Additionally, the rolling spillovers from both CSM and FEX to natural gas are generally more significant compared to other markets. On the contrary, the rolling spillovers from CSM to oil are generally more significant compared to the spillovers from FEX. Regarding the directional predictability, it is observed that for the gold market, there is consistent directional predictability from FEX across the entire duration of the observation period. Conversely, for the oil market, the spillover effects from CSM to oil are stronger compared to the other way around. Moreover, for the natural gas market, there is consistent and significant directional predictability from both CSM and FEX across the entire duration of the observation period.

The research indicates a considerable impact of both the CSM and USDCNY exchange rates on commodity prices. The performance of the CSM is a key driver of demand for energy commodities including oil and natural gas; conversely, an appreciating U.S. dollar generally leads to lower gold prices. The market's influence has significant consequences for conservation initiatives. Significant expansion in the Certified Sustainable Materials sector could suggest increased resource extraction, placing pressure on vulnerable ecosystems. Concurrently, changes in exchange rates may affect conservation funding, especially for entities holding gold-based assets. Conservationists can improve their

responsiveness by using CSM and exchange rate trends as early warning systems, enabling proactive safeguarding of at-risk areas and diversified funding to lessen market volatility. Policymakers should concurrently promote sustainable practices within CSM-listed companies and advocate for resource extraction limits that are flexible and respond to market dynamics. These strategies, when implemented concurrently, can fortify environmental protection against economic volatility.

5 Conclusion

The

Fig. 7 Rolling Cross-Quantilogram Daily Return Spillovers for oil. The top panel of the graph specifically examines the spillover effect from the Chinese Stock Market and Exchange Rate to oil, with a focus on the 1-day ahead rolling spillover. The analysis is conducted at three quantiles: a low level ($\alpha=0.1$), a median ($\alpha=0.5$) and ($\alpha=0.9$) from the left to right.

comprehensive analysis of spillover effects between the CSM, FEX, and CMP, specifically focusing on Gold, Natural Gas, and Oil, has revealed significant insights. The use of CQ methods enabled a nuanced understanding of how these markets interact across different quantiles and market conditions. It was found that spillover effects are dependent on quantiles, which indicate that CSM, CSM, and FEX may be context in which the market is at a low, median, or high return. Gold has positive spillover effects from CSM during high returns in stock markets further justifying its position as a 'safe' asset in times of doubt. Correspondingly, Natural Gas and Oil have high positive spillovers throughout economic expansion because of the effects of the Chinese stock market on global energy demand. On the other hand, the US dollar-based CNY exchange rate has negative effect on the spillovers of commodities like Gold and Oil but only in a

higher quantile. This shows the role of currency fluctuations in the pricing of commodities. The study also pointed out that there are links between China's financial markets and those of common commodities markets in the world especially in times of economic downturns.

From the conclusions of this study, it is recommended that traders and investors use mixed or diversified strategies to reduce the expected spillover risk from CSM and FEX. As the study indicates, spillovers are not a constant due to the existence of different market conditions, therefore, diverse investors may apply quantile targeting trading strategies. For instance, during firmer stock markets, targeting the quantile position of commodities like Gold or Oil and reaching for their oil stock can add value to the overall portfolio. Also, the analysis on commodities illustrates that currency fluctuations especially USDCNY exchange rate substantially influence commodities and therefore forex dynamics should be observed closely. Currency options or futures hedging strategies may limit the downside risk caused by unfavorable currency fluctuations especially during turbulence markets. Further, they will also limit their vulnerability by expanding their exposures across nonrelated asset types such as energy commodities and safe-haven assets, which are expected to suppress risks in cases of a downturn or upturn.

The implications of this study are also useful for policymakers in China's energy-importing countries which are heavily reliant on China's commodity market. Given the strong herding behavior spillover from CSM to Oil and Natural Gas, it is imperative that these countries formulate appropriate measures to insulate against demand shocks caused by fluctuations in the Chinese stock market. These measures may consist of accumulating stocks when demand is low or hedging when indicators point to stronger demand for commodities. In addition, the negative spillovers of the USDCNY into the price structures of Gold and Oil necessitate a policy objective geared towards stabilisation of foreign exchange markets. Effective management of the exchange rate may reduce adverse impacts on the prices of commodities that are important in the context of balance of payments as well as internal trade. Also, parameters governing exchange rate policies that avoid excessive volatility may also be able to assist commodity markets that are important for economic growth and stability in the long run.

The conclusions of the study set the stage for the following research. Geopolitical turbulence or world financial instability can be integrated into the model by the researchers to further investigate their effect on the forecasting outcomes associated with the entire commodity price. The CQ method allows researchers to examine the influence of various global factors on the link between the stock market, the currency market, and commodity markets. Furthermore, the analysis should be expanded to include other commodities as well as other developing economies to have a better perspective on the extent of globalization within the context of worldwide commodity trading. More advanced research can also be carried out and combined with real-time data to model high-frequency trading and understand the nature of instantaneous spillover effects. This would enable investors and policymakers to have a rapid response to a sudden market shock especially in high global levels of uncertainty.

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